

Multi-Criteria Decision Making for Marine Propulsion: Hybrid, Diesel Electrical and Diesel Mechanical Systems from Cost- Environment-Risk Perspectives

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Abstract

The paper aims to introduce an effective decision making process as well as to evaluate the excellence of the hybrid ship as presenting a case study where the performance of a hybrid ship was compared with that of equivalent ship with conventional propulsion systems (diesel electrical and diesel mechanical ones) from the cost, environmental and risk perspectives. This paper provides an overview of the modern approaches of multi-criteria decision-making and highlights their shortcomings particularly associated with the techniques for converting different units in each criterion into a single comparable unit for decision-making. To remedy this issue, this paper has placed a particular emphasis on enhancing the process of multi-criteria decision analysis. The key of the proposed process is to convert incomparable units in each criterion into the monetary value, thereby enabling the impacts of each criterion to be compared and integrated straightforward. In addition, this process algorithm covers the analysis of scenario optimization where different scenarios are applied into the proposed decision-making process. Results of the case study ascertained that the use of hybrid system could achieve about

\$ 300,000 (about 2 % holistic cost reduction) by comparison with diesel electric propulsion system while almost \$ 1 million (about 7 % holistic cost reduction) by comparison with diesel mechanical system under the current operational practice. An optimal operation was also proven that the operating hybrid mode during manoeuvring and berthing is more desirable as it can reduce almost \$ 1 million. Moreover, the efficiency of the proposed process was verified by comparison with the results obtained from the conventional decision-making process using analytical hierarchical method. It is believed that the research findings not only support stakeholders to understand the excellence of hybrid, but provides them with insight into the optimal approach for multi-criteria decision analysis.

Keywords: Hybrid ship, Multi-criteria decision analysis, Hybrid propulsion, MCDA

Lists of symbols

C_E	Energy cost
C_{EC}	Cost for Economic impact
C_{EI}	Cost for environmental impact
$C_{F,i}$	Fixed cost at i
C_{GWP}	Cost for tCO ₂ e
C_k	Cost for emission substance, k
C_{RI}	Cost of risk impact
C_{RPN}	Cost of RPN value '1'
C_T	Total cost
$C_{v,j}$	Variable costs at j
EI_{GWP}	Total global warming potential
EI_k	Environmental impact of emission substance, k.
EF_j	Emission factor at emission substance, j
EF_k	Emission factor at emission substance, k
EM	Electricity margin (20%)
EP	Electricity price
FC_i	Fuel consumption at propulsion load, i
FP	Fuel price
GWP_j	Global warming potential at emission substance, i
RPN_h	RPN at hazard, h
SM	Sea margin (20%)
$SFOC_i$	Specific oil consumption at propulsion load, i
t_i	Time spent at propulsion load, i

1. Introduction

1.1. Overview of hybrid ships

While almost every industry is striving to develop more efficient and clearer process and products, the hybrid technologies have remarkably attracted the attention of the marine industry. As a result, the advent of hybrid ships has been witnessed over the last few years that were a monumental time when it comes to the improvement of battery technologies.

With an advantage of enhancing the flexibility of using power sources [1], *MV Viking Lady*, the world's first hybrid ship equipped with a 500 kW battery system, was launched in 2013. Then, a series of hybrid ships did not take long to follow: the new offshore supply vessel of *MV Edda Ferd* in 2013 and the first large electric battery-powered car ferry, *MV Ampere* in 2015 [2]. For domestic services, three hybrid ro-ro passenger ferries, namely *MV Lochinvar* in 2011, *MV Hallaig* in 2013 and *MV Catriona* in 2016 are presently operated across the coasts of Scotland, UK [3].

On the other hand, various reports and researches have revealed that hybrid ships can significantly contribute to reducing fuel consumptions, thereby air emissions during sea-borne trades. Lindstad and Sandaas [4] have evaluated the environmental impact of hybrid offshore support vessels using dynamic positioning system and presented the excellence of hybrid systems, compared with conventional diesel electrical system. Ling-Chin and Roskilly [5] have applied a new approach of life cycle assessment to evaluate the environmental impact of hybrid ro-ro cargo vessel, whereas Dedes et al. [6] have investigated the performance of hybrid system for slow speed ocean going ships in the fuel reduction points. In addition, Wang et al. [7] have applied the methods of life cycle and life cycle cost analyses for a short route hybrid ferry. The results of their researches commonly addressed that the energy saving would be achieved by proper handling of energy systems associated with main and auxiliary engines.

Lan et al. [8] introduced an analysis model to estimate an optimal sizing of hybrid systems in combination of Photovoltaic (PV), diesel and battery for ship propulsion. In the research, five scenarios in different navigation routes were modelled. Similarly, Wen et al. [9] developed an interval optimization method to investigate the optimal size of an energy storage system (ESS) combined with the solar power system. By diversifying ship engine loads, the research results were compared in terms of fuel cost and emissions, thereby the optimal system was evaluated.

Diab et al. [10] has compared onshore hybrid renewable systems with the equivalent sets of on-board systems, revealing that the combination of the solar and battery systems can improve the efficiency of ship performance and reduce the emissions and total costs for both onshore and on-board systems.

While the previous researches have proved that the hybrid ship is advantageous in terms of fuel savings and less emissions, there was a lack of the systematic investigation of the performance of hybrid ships in consideration of the multiple criteria: cost, environmental impact and risk. Furthermore, the hybrid systems in the marine industry are still new concepts, thereby somewhat limited in design and operational practices. In this context, it may be necessary to investigate the optimal operation of hybrid modes. Therefore, this paper was motivated to investigate the feasibility of hybrid ships by means of multi-criteria decision making analysis.

1.2. Overview of multi-criteria decision making process

Proper decision making is always essential for success in all industries. When considering a single criterion, the decision may be simply made by comparing the value of the criterion with an equivalent set of alternatives. If various criteria are taken into account, the decision-making process will be much more complex as one should investigate the impact of each criterion and develop a method to convert the impact of such criteria into a single comparable unit [11].

Needless to say, the complexity of multi-dimensionality applied to the decision making for a design or system selection has been across the industries.

Not surprisingly, there have been several the multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods introduced. For example, Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT), Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Outranking are regarded as common MCDA methods [12-19].

In addition to the common methods, a number of researches have introduced different process to optimize MCDA. Linkov and Seager [20] have developed a concept of coupling MCDA that accounts for environmental and risk impacts for emerging threats. This approach integrated the impact of each category, enabling a base design to be compared with alternatives. They showed the coupling of the risk assessment with life cycle assessment can enhance the risk management. However, the fact that the birthplace of this method is in the human health and medical industry diminishes the application to marine technology to some extent. Moreover, this research has remained some uncertainties about detailed methods for life cycle assessment and risk assessment.

Basurko and Mesbahi [21] presented an integrated quantitative approach for the holistic assessment of the marine technologies in terms of environmental, economic and social sustainability. The analysis was carried out by means of standard life cycle assessment and economic evaluation method as well as a new method for evaluating the social sustainability.

In the proposed approach, all three criteria could be scored at the range between 0 and 100.

Niekamp et al. [22] structured a framework for a multi-criteria decision in relation to the sustainability of an asset management. With the proposed method, decision-makers can assign certain levels of weight to the scores on each criterion based on their own knowledge or preference. This method was applied to a case study on evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of material alternatives, compared to the conventional carbon steel in the marine industry. Regarding a function of weighting, weighting values are still needed to be defined by

users or stakeholders; hence, the results of the analysis are destined to overly rely on what values are weighted on each criterion.

On the other hand, there have various application of MCDA methods in the similar research areas. In order to select the most cost-effective measures for emissions reduction, Yuan and Ng [23] have introduced a ranking algorithm that was applied for ranking feasible shipping reduction measures with a new criterion in consideration of cost in consideration of the preference between cost and benefits. Dong et al. [24] evaluated the optimal municipal waste management system in terms of energy efficiency, environmental friendliness and economy. The method of weighing factors have been extensively used; to investigate the optimal wind farm siting [25-26]; to optimize biomass briquette fuel system [27]; to investigate optimal siting and size of bioenergy facilities [28-29]; to apply environmental criteria to assess the performance of product suppliers [30-31].

Given that each criterion has different levels of impact on making a decision, the analysis appeared to have some inherent limitations on converting the inconsistent units into a single comparable value because these approaches do not reflect the priority of the categories that may be differently assigned by different stockholders. In order to prioritize different criteria in view of the stakeholders' interests, certain levels of weight are given to the scores on each criterion based on their own knowledge or preference. The overreliance on personal judgements may lead to misleading conclusions, or cause undesirable decision-making. If a value is weighted more heavily, the results may be concluded in an improper way. That leaves plenty of room for shading the right decision.

Wang et al. [32] have reviewed and compared several models of weighting factors based on different criteria. They investigated the influence of weighting factors on decision making of sustainable energy selection, taking into account the multi-dimensional nature of sustainability goals and the complexity of socio-economic and biophysical systems.

However, one key challenge to assign weighting factors on different categories based on the subjective information provided by the stakeholders was addressed by several researches [33-36]. With debates on weighing factors for decision-making [11], since 1979 when Dawes [37] has addressed the results would be biased by weighing methods, the practice of giving equal weights to each category have been widely adopted. However, this practice still fails to reflect the actual impacts of values in different criteria. To make the analysis more reliable, sensitivity analysis may be required.

1.3. Research motivation

Moving onto a hybrid system, this paper aimed to investigate and compare the different values of cost, environment and risk. As their units are inherently different, the direct comparison may not be possible; basic unit of the economic impact is monetary term while those of environmental and risk impacts are the quantity of air emissions and the risk level respectively. In this context, the key lesson from the previous research is to pay attention to the disparity in the unit of analysis. The most desirable way is to convert all of the categories to be analysed into the same unit, through which the application of weighing factors on each category becomes unnecessary process. In this regard, this paper was born to introduce a new framework for an optimal decision making to fulfil this gap.

With the proposed approach, the feasibility study of the hybrid ro-ro ferry, *MV Catriona*, was systematically assessed and compared with conventional ship types - diesel electric (DE) and diesel mechanical (DM) propulsion systems.

2. Description of proposed method

Taking into account the background and limitations of the conventional decision-making approaches,

Fig. 1 outlines an enhanced decision-making framework with which economic, environmental and risk impacts are to be firstly assessed. The assessment results in each category, then, are converted into the monetary terms as a comparable unit. Therefore, the overall impact of a proposed design or product can be finally obtained by the combination of all monetary values converted from the individual impacts.

A noticeable benefit of this approach is placed on eliminating the process of the normalization and weighting factors. Instead, the combination of three monetary values obtained in different models are used for decision-making straightforward without any other subjective assumptions. This process can be repeated with the number of models ($1...M$) and their results, therefore, are compared and used to determine the optimal model.

On the other hand, in order to investigate the sensitivity of variables or uncertainties on the analysis results, this framework is to identify all the possible scenarios ($1...N$) and analyse them throughout the proposed processes. By comparison with the results obtained from the sensitivity analysis, it will obtain the optimal decision-making as well as general trends of the parametric influences on the final decision.

Fig. 1. Schematic of SHIPLYS LCT concept.

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2.1. *Economic impact assessment*

Fig. 2 specifies the process of economic impact assessment (Task 1) tailored to the scope of the present research. It starts with the data collection with which the energy consumption of the proposed model is estimated. It, then, moves into the process of cost estimation where Eq. (1) is used to calculate the energy expenses.

Fig. 2. Outlines for Task 1 – economic impact assessment (estimating variable cost).

$$C_E = \sum_{i=0}^n (SFOC_i \times FC_i \times FP \times SM + EC_i \times EP \times EM) \times t_i \quad (1)$$

Given that the holistic cost of a ship is comprised of various expenses spent during the life cycle of the ship, this paper simply categorizes the overall ship cost into two types; one is ‘fixed cost’ that is insensitive to the change in the selected models for decision-making while the other is ‘variable cost’ sensitive to the model changes. The variable cost for the present study on comparing the performance of a hybrid ship with two other conventional ship types is defined as the capital and operational costs in relation to various propulsion systems, whereas all the other costs are considered as fixed cost. Finally, the economic impact of a model can be expressed as the combination of all fixed and variable costs as shown in Eq. (2).

$$C_{EC} = \sum_{i=0}^n C_{F,i} \times \sum_{j=0}^m C_{V,j} \quad (2)$$

2.2. *Environmental impact assessment*

Since marine vessels are attributed to different types of environmental impacts such as global warming, acidification, eutrophication, etc. [4], Fig. 3 shows the process of Task 2, environmental impact assessment. Given the scope of this paper, Task 2 is designed to investigate the variation of environmental impact obtained from different configuration of propulsion systems: hybrid, DE and DM. Similar to Task 1, it starts with collecting data on emission types, their quantities and costs.

Fig. 3. Outlines for Task 2 – environment impact assessment.

As shown in Table 1, International Maritime Organization (IMO) provides a general guideline of emission factors of eight major emissions produced from the exhaust gas of diesel engines in accordance with fuel types. Based on this, this process quantifies air emissions.

Table 1 Emission factors for top-down emissions from combustion of fuels [38].

Emissions substance	GWP (tCO ₂ e)	Marine MGO emissions factor (g/g fuel)
CO ₂	1	3.20600
CH ₄	25	0.00006
N ₂ O	265	0.00015
NO _x	×	0.08725
CO	0.027	0.00277

NMVOC	×	0.00308
SO _x	×	0.00264
PM ₂₅	×	0.00102

In order to assess the costs of the emissions, the marginal external costs of air emissions reported in several EU projects where 29 EU countries have evaluated the practical cost values of emissions for water ways are applied [39-41]. They provides various cost factors for CO₂, NO_x, SO_x, NMVOC (non-methane volatile organic compound) and PM₂₅ (particulate matters from exhaust) in accordance with different EU nations.

On the other hand, the emissions of CO₂, CH₄, CO and N₂O are converted into global warming potential (GWP) and calculated with CO₂ costs. Therefore, environmental impact for GWP can be calculated by using Eq. (3).

$$EI_{GWP} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m FC_i \times (EF_j \times GWP_j) \quad (3)$$

Other emission impacts are calculated in the same way as shown in Eq. (4).

$$EI_k = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^l FC_i \times EF_k \quad (4)$$

Therefore, using Eq. (5), the environmental impact can be converted into the monetary terms.

$$C_{EI} = C_{GWP} \times EI_{GWP} + \sum_{i=k}^l C_k \times EI_k \quad (5)$$

2.3. Risk assessment

Fig. 4 shows an overview of the proposed risk assessment, which is basically divided into two steps: 1) risk assessment 2) conversion of the results into monetary terms.#

This process basically adopted an approach of qualitative risk assessment by using failure mode effect criticality assessment (FMECA) with which the failure modes of a mechanical or electrical system are widely identified as well as frequency, consequence and mitigation measures of individual hazards are assessed in aids either of subjective or objective information. Based on FMECA, the process of risk assessment is modified and integrated with decision-making process accordingly.

Fig. 4. Outlines for Task 3 – risk impact assessment.

2.3.1. Risk assessment

The first step of risk assessment is to identify the potential hazards (failure modes of proposed systems). Then, three key parameters are used for assessing the risk of individual hazards.

- Occurrence (O) provides details about the probability of an accident;
- Severity (S) deals with a severity of identified hazards;
- Mitigation (M) represents the chances of detection of failures before they arise or the coverage by backup systems.

The product of the three parameters provides the risk level known as the risk priority number (RPN). Table 2 to Table 4 show the different scales used to measure the three parameters O, S and M. The RPN is expressed as the combination of O, S, and, D as shown in Eq. (6).

$$RPN = O \times S \times D \tag{6}$$

Table 2 Frequency scales [42].

Rank	Probability of failures	Human error occurrence Probability	Linguistic Variable
1	<1:20000	< every 5 years	Unlikely
2	1:20000	In 3-5 years	Low FR
3	1:10000	In 1-3 years	
4	1:2000	Per year	Occasional F
5	1:1000	In every 6 months	
6	1:200	In every 3 months	
7	1:100	Per months	Repeated F
8	1:20	Per week	
9	1:10	Every few days	Inevitable
10	1:2	Per day	

Table 3 Consequence scale [42].

Severity of each effect of failure or error	Effect	Rank
No reason to expect failure to have any effect on safety, health, environment or mission	None	1

Very minor effect on product or system performance to have any effect on safety or health. The system does not require repair.	Very minor	2
Minor effect on product or system performance to have any effect on safety or health. The system can require repair.	Minor	3
Very low effect on system performance. A failure is not serious enough to cause injury, property damage, or system damage, but can result in unscheduled maintenance or repair.	Low	4
Moderate effect on system performance. The system requires repair. A failure which may cause moderate injury, moderate property damage, or moderate system damage which will result in delay or loss of system availability or mission degradation. 100% of mission may need to be reworked or process delayed.	Moderate	5
System performance is degraded. Some safety functions may not operate. A failure causes injury, property damage, or system damage. Some portion of mission is lost. High delaying restoring function.	Significant	6
System performance is severely affected but functions (reduced level of safety performance).The system may not operate. Failure does not involve noncompliance with government regulations or standards.	Major	7
The system is inoperable with loss of primary function. Failure can involve hazardous outcomes and/or noncompliance with government regulations or standards.	Extreme	8
Failure involves hazardous outcomes and/or noncompliance with government regulations or standards. Potential safety, health or environmental issue. Failure will occur with a warning.	Very extreme	9
Failure is hazardous and occurs without warning. It affects safe operation. A failure is serious enough to cause injury, property damage, or system damage. Failure will occur without warning.	Serious	10

Table 4 Mitigation scale [42].

Likelihood of detection of failure or error	Degree of importance	Probability of failure detection %	Rank
Current control(s) almost certainly will detect a potential failure mode/task error. Reliable controls are known with a similar process.	Almost certain	0-5	1
Very likelihood current control(s) will detect failure modes/task error. Controls are able to detect within the same machine/module (almost always preceded by a warning).	Very high	5-15	2
High chance the design control(s) will almost certainly detect a potential failure Mode/task error. Controls are able to detect within the same function area.	High	15-25	3
Moderately high likelihood current control(s) will detect failure modes/task error.	Moderately high	25-35	4
Moderate chance that the design control will detect a potential failure mode/task error, or the defect will remain undetected until the system performance is affected.	Moderately	35-45	5
Low likelihood current control(s) will detect failure modes/task error (program or operator is not likely to detect a potential design weakness).	Low	45-55	6
Very low likelihood current control(s) will detect failure modes/task error (program or	Very low	55-65	7

Operator will not to detect a potential design weakness).			
Remote chance that the design control will detect a potential failure mode/task error, Or the defect will remain undetected until an inspection or test is carried out.	Remote	75-85	8
Defect most likely remains undetected (very remote chance that the design control will detect a potential cause/mechanism and subsequent failure modes) or the task will be performed in the presence of the defect	Very remote	85-95	9
System failures are not detected (design control will not and/or cannot detect a potential cause/mechanism and subsequent failure modes) or there is no design verification or the task will certainly be performed in the presence of the defect.	Almost impossible	90-100	10

2.3.2. Conversion into monetary terms

Fig. 5. Principle for cost estimation in accordance with RPN.

Fig. 5 illustrates the principle for converting the RPN into the monetary terms. The RPN is technically ranked between 1 and 1,000. In the proposed process, the RPN 1,000 is assumed to represent the worst case equivalent to the total loss of the ship. Hence, the cost value of the RPN 1,000 equals the total cost of the ship. Then, the unit value of RPN '1' can be determined when the cost of RPN 1,000 is divided by 1,000. Let say, if the cost of the total loss is \$1 million equivalent to RPN 1,000, the value of RPN '1' is \$1,000. Nevertheless, this unit RPN can vary depending on the conditions and the scope of study.

$$C_{RI} = \sum_{h=1}^O (RPN_h \times C_{RPN}) \quad (7)$$

2.4. Optimal decision-making

The overall costs for economic, environmental and risk impacts of proposed models are presented by means of Eq. (8). The results in different models are compared one another, thereby determining the optimal decision-making by selecting the model with the lowest total cost.

$$C_T = C_{EC} + C_{EV} + C_{RI} \quad (8)$$

3. Case study

3.1. Description

The selected hybrid ro-ro ferry, MV *Catriona*, is presently engaged in the coastal service between the route of Claonaig - Lochranza, Scotland, UK since its initial delivery in September 2016. It was equipped with two lithium-ion batteries (350 kW each) and integrated with the diesel electric propulsion systems. Basic specifications are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5 General characteristics of MV *Catriona* [3].

Tonnage:	135 DWT
Length:	43.5 m (143 ft)
Beam:	12.2 m (40 ft)

Draught:	1.73 m (5 ft 8 in)
Installed power:	For hybrid system: 3 × 360kW generator + 2 × Lithium Ion batteries 350 kW each (actual) For DE system : 2 × 360 kW G/E (imaginary) For DM system: 2 × 450 kW M/E and 1 × 50 kW G/E (imaginary)
Propulsion:	Voith 16 R5 EC/90-1 Units
Speed:	9 knots
Capacity:	150 passengers; 23 cars
Route:	Claonaig - Lochranza, UK
Fuel type	Marine gas oil (MGO)

Having the hybrid concept, the case ship was designed to be operated either by electricity from diesel generator engines or lithium-ion batteries. It can be also operated with both power sources. In short, the case ship runs in three modes: diesel mode, battery mode and hybrid mode.

Fig. 6. Drawing for MV Catrina [3].

Fig. 6 shows a brief diagram for electricity load distribution for the case ship. In diesel mode, the electricity generated from the diesel generators are transmitted to the Main Switchboard. The electricity, then, is distributed where needed; in particular, it is used to control the speed of motors via variable speed drives. Therefore, the propulsion unit connected with the motors are controlled. In battery mode, on board batteries replace the diesel generators as the electricity from the batteries are directly supplied to the variable speed drives, prompting the propulsion. On the other hand, in hybrid mode, both batteries and generators are connected together to supply the propulsion power, meaning that the propulsion loads of generators are shared with batteries.

Based on the proposed voyage and associated engine loads, energy consumptions were estimated as shown in Table 6. In the table, proposed power loads for imaginary ships for DE and DM are also described.

Table 6 General characteristics of MV Catriona [3].

Service route		Claonaig - Lochranza					
Operation profile		Transit		Manoeuvring		At Slip	
One voyage (minute)		40		4		16-46	
Average daily voyage (minute)		360		36		224	
Power demand (kW) for hybrid and DE / DM		322 / 291		144 / 130		87 / 78	
Propulsion type	Hybrid (current practice)	72 %	1 G/E + 2 batteries (20%)	40 %	1 G/E	24 %	1 G/E
	Hybrid (optional)	45 %	2 G/E	0 %	2 batteries	0 %	2 batteries
	DE	45 %	2 G/E	40 %	1 G/E	24 %	1 G/E
	DM	32 %	2 M/E +1 G/E	14 %	2 M/E +1 G/E	9 %	2 M/E +1 G/E

Since engines are not to exceed the 75 % of the total load for the safety reason, it can be found that the hybrid ships can take an advantage from running a single engine during the transit

while DE and DM are required two engines. In addition, the ship with DM is required for an independent diesel generator to cover electrical service loads.

Fig. 7. Estimated ship load profile in the proposed voyage (for six month operation).

Fig. 7 shows the estimation of shipload profile in the proposed voyage (for six-month operation). Based on this, the energy consumptions are estimated. To investigate the adequacy of this estimation, the calculation results are compared with actual on-board records of energy consumption collected since the case ship was delivered in late 2016. Fig. 8 shows daily energy consumption of MV Catriona during the six month time between October 2016 and March 2017.

In the principle of hybrid operation, during daily operation, in general, battery supplies 20 % of shipload while G/E for 80 %. In addition, about 20 % battery remaining after daily operation. On the other hand, when the weather condition is adverse full G/E was operated in parallel without batteries. Charging time of battery takes 11 hours by means of the onshore power grid.

Fig. 8. Daily energy consumption of MV Catriona.

Fig. 9. Operational mode for six month operation.

Given in Fig. 9, the operation was basically made in hybrid mode while occasionally diesel only mode was applied in particular of when the weather condition was adverse. Moreover, often the schedules were cancelled either by adverse weather conditions or maintenance purposes. Based on the actual operational data and records monitored by the on-board systems the total fuel consumption was estimated at 95,123 litres with the actual battery consumption measured by the on-board monitoring system was 60,170 kWh during the six month operation. Using the analytical model the results shows 91,042 litres (97.0 %) for fuel consumption while 57,500 kWh (95.5 %) for battery consumption. Therefore, the analytical model is to be perceived efficient. Given the operational data, the case ship is assumed to be operated 313 days for a year time.

3.2. *Analysis based on initial (actual) scenario*

The first scenario was set up based on the actual practice of operating hybrid systems with which the performance of hybrid ship was compared with those of DE and DM. There are some information/assumptions to be noted as below;

- Using MGO for ship operation, \$ 479.5 / metric ton (assessed on 6th Sep. 2017 [43]).
- Electricity costs are estimated at \$ 0.08 / kWh at night time charge [44].
- UK based environmental costs: GWP for \$ 24/tCO₂e, NO_x for \$ 4,602/ton SO_x for \$ 7,788/ton PM₂₅ for \$ 71,626/ton, and NMVOC for \$ 1,298/ton.
- Costs of total loss (equivalent to RPN 1000) are hybrid for \$ 12,187,000, DE for \$ 12,014,940 and DM for \$ 12,000,000.

Engine maintenance intervals, replaceable items and associated costs were driven from the manufacture's information (MAN Diesel). From the analysis, the engine maintenance costs were evaluated as \$ 4.4 /h for a 360 kW engine while \$5.4/h for a 450 kW engine and the results are plotted in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Engine operation hours vs maintenance costs.

Table 7 shows the comparison of economic and environmental impacts across hybrid, DE and DM models. Results show that hybrid system is relatively advantageous in environmental impact than other two models while the DE system is more economical in energy costs.

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Table 7 Results of economic and environmental impact assessment.

	Hybrid	DE	DM
Economic impact			
Ship price	\$12,215,140.00	\$12,014,940.00	\$12,000,000.00
Energy price	\$1,430,984.68	\$1,104,531.63	\$1,164,972.20
engine maintenance costs	\$364,988.00	\$592,328.00	\$882,290.00
Total	\$14,011,112.68	\$13,711,799.63	\$14,047,262.20
Environmental impact (life time)			
GWP	\$519,446.97	\$559,860.51	\$590,496.38
NO _x	\$2,351,094.65	\$2,534,012.37	\$2,672,674.89
SO _x	\$120,389.31	\$129,755.73	\$136,856.04
PM ₂₅	\$427,788.33	\$461,070.73	\$486,300.77

NMVOC	\$23,409.03	\$25,230.28	\$26,610.90
Total	\$3,442,128.30	\$3,709,929.62	\$3,912,938.97

Similarly, the risk impact assessment was carried out based on the electrical diagrams as presented through Fig. 6 for hybrid, Fig. 11 for DE and Fig. 12 for DM. The results are presented in Table 8 to Table 10.

Table 8 Results of risk assessment for Hybrid propulsion system.

No	Hazard	FI	CI	MI	RPN	Costs	Safety guards
1	No.1 Battery bank fails during normal operation	1	2	1	4	\$48,860.56	Switch to No.2 Battery bank or Switch to DE mode. May need to repair the failure part.
2	No.2 Battery bank fails during normal operation	1	2	1	4	\$48,860.56	Switch to No.1 Battery bank or Switch to DE mode. May need to repair the failure part.
3	No.1 Motor Fails during normal operation	2	6	2	24	\$293,163.36	No.2 motor is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
4	No.2 Motor Fails during normal operation	2	6	2	24	\$293,163.36	No.1 motor is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
5	No.1 DC Variable speed drives fails during normal operation	1	6	2	12	\$146,581.68	No.2 motor is only used for propulsion (No.1 motor is out of control) Urgently need to repair the failure part.
6	No.2 DC Variable speed drives fails during normal operation	1	6	2	12	\$146,581.68	No.1 motor is only used for propulsion (No.2 motor is out of control) Urgently need to repair the failure part.
7	AFT battery charger fails	1	1	1	1	\$12,215.14	FWD battery charger can be used. May need to repair the failure part.
8	FWD battery charger fails	1	1	1	1	\$12,215.14	AFT battery charger can be used. May need to repair the failure part.
9	No.1 G/E fails	2	2	1	2	\$24,430.28	No.2 & 3 G/E can be used. Hybrid can be still useful.
10	No.2 G/E fails	2	2	1	2	\$24,430.28	No.1 & 3 G/E can be used. Hybrid can be still useful.
11	No.3 G/E fails	2	2	1	2	\$24,430.28	No.1 & 2 G/E can be used. Hybrid can be still useful.
##	Total					\$1,074,932.32	

Fig. 11. Drawing for DE propulsion system [3].

Table 9 Results of risk assessment for DE propulsion system.

No	Hazard	FI	CI	MI	RPN	Costs	Remark
1	No.1 Motor Fails during normal operation	2	6	2	24	\$288,358.56	No.2 motor is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
2	No.2 Motor Fails during normal operation	2	6	2	24	\$288,358.56	No.1 motor is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
3	No.1 DC Variable speed drives fails during normal operation	1	6	2	12	\$144,179.28	No.2 motor is only used for propulsion (No.1 motor is out of control) Urgently need to repair the failure part.
4	No.2 DC Variable speed drives fails during normal operation	1	6	2	12	\$144,179.28	No.1 motor is only used for propulsion (No.2 motor is out of control) Urgently need to repair the failure part.
5	No.1 G/E fails	2	4	2	16	\$192,239.04	No.2 & 3 G/E can be used. Ship speed may need to be reduced. May need to repair the failure part.
6	No.2 G/E fails	2	4	2	16	\$192,239.04	No.1 & 3 G/E can be used. Ship speed may need to be reduced. May need to repair the failure part.
7	No.3 G/E fails	2	4	2	16	\$192,239.04	No.1 & 2 G/E can be used. Ship speed may need to be reduced. May need to repair the failure part.

Total	\$1,441,792.80
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Fig. 12. Drawing for DM propulsion system [3].

Table 10 Results of risk assessment for DM propulsion system.

No	Hazard	FI	CI	MI	RPN	Costs	Remark
1	No.1 Main Engine fails	2	7	2	28	\$336,000.00	No.2 Main engine is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
2	No.2 Main Engine fails	2	7	2	28	\$336,000.00	No.1 Main engine is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
3	No.1 G/E fails	2	5	2	20	\$240,000.00	No.2 G/E back up can be used
4	No2 G/E fails	2	5	2	20	\$240,000.00	No.1 G/E back up can be used.
5	No.1 propulsion shaft failure	2	7	2	28	\$336,000.00	No.2 Main engine is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
6	No.2 propulsion shaft failure	2	7	2	28	\$336,000.00	No.1 Main engine is only used for propulsion. Urgently need to repair the failure part.
	Total					\$1,824,000.00	

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For a verification work, the estimated costs in relation to the individual failure mode, expressed as the RPN were scrutinized with the Caledonian MacBrayne Ltd., the current operator of the case ship (MV Catriona). Based on their actual history and estimates of system repair and maintenance, it was agreed that the estimated costs of individual risks would be placed at reasonably probable levels.

Fig. 13. Analysis results based on initial (actual) scenario.

As shown in Fig. 13, the results of analysis for the initial scenario are expressed as the total cost, thereby enabling the users to make an optimal decision straightforward. The total cost of Hybrid ship was estimated at \$18,163,185.30 while DE was at \$18,271,194.06 and DM was at \$18,901,911.17 respectively. The results proven that the ro-ro ferry with hybrid system is the most desirable option overall in showing that the total cost of the option is the lowest. In the opposite way, DM system is less desirable than other options. Despite relatively higher economic impact, hybrid system outperforms other models overall.

3.3. *Analysis for alternative scenarios*

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The initial analysis has been carried out based on the six month operational data and assumed that the case ship will be under the same condition over the life time. It certainly drew meaningful results for hybrid ships. However, in reality, it is not certain the service areas and environmental conditions, thereby its fuel consumptions. In this regards, this paper analyses additional scenarios.

This case study was originally carried out base on the actual operational practice of the hybrid ship. On the other hand, as presented in the Section 2, the process of the proposed decision-making process was to estimate the optimal decision making while investigating various scenarios and influences of the differences of the scenarios on the results.

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3.3.1. Optimization of hybrid mode

As discussed earlier, the current practice of the battery usage is 80 % for G/Es and 20 % for batteries during the transit mode while the batteries are switched off during manoeuvring and berthing modes. Whether the current practice of battery usage is optimal can be an issue.

Therefore, an alternative scenario for hybrid operation was proposed. This scenario assumes that the hybrid is operated during manoeuvring and berthing rather than transit mode in replace of diesel generates. For transit mode, two diesel generators are operated in parallel. The results were compared with these obtained from the actual (initial) scenario as shown in Fig. 14. It shows that the hybrid operation during the manoeuvring and berthing is slightly better off than the initial practice revealing that the economic and environmental impacts may be affected by selecting operational scenario to some extent.

Fig. 14. Analysis results, compared to optimal scenarios.

3.3.2. Sensitivity analysis for emission prices

Since the current study was focused on the hybrid ship in the UK, the price of emissions was estimated based on the UK market prices. However, as shown in Table 11, the wide range of emission prices across the EU nations indicates that the service area of the hybrid ship may also have an influence on the overall results of decision-making. In this regard, it may be worth of investigating the sensitivity of emission prices, thereby evaluating environmental impact changes for the different geometrical area. For simple comparison, two scenarios - one with the highest emission costs and the other with the lowest emission costs - were investigated.

Table 11 Prices of emissions in accordance with EU nations.

	NOx	NM VOC	SO ₂	PM _{2.5} (exhaust)		
				urban	outside	CO ₂
Austria	\$10,266.00	\$2,006.00	\$9,794.00	\$489,700.00	\$32,804.00	-
Belgium	\$6,136.00	\$2,950.00	\$12,980.00	\$498,196.00	\$43,070.00	-

Bulgaria	\$2,124.00	\$236.00	\$1,180.00	\$50,740.00	\$5,192.00	-
Cyprus	\$590.00	\$354.00	\$2,360.00	\$287,566.00	\$9,676.00	-
Czech Republic	\$8,614.00	\$1,180.00	\$9,440.00	\$298,068.00	\$29,618.00	-
Denmark	\$5,192.00	\$826.00	\$6,136.00	\$456,424.00	\$21,476.00	\$26.00
Estonia	\$944.00	\$118.00	\$2,124.00	\$157,412.00	\$10,620.00	-
Finland	\$944.00	\$236.00	\$2,124.00	\$397,778.00	\$13,216.00	\$65.00
France	\$9,086.00	\$1,652.00	\$9,440.00	\$462,796.00	\$37,052.00	\$25.00
Germany	\$11,328.00	\$2,006.00	\$12,980.00	\$453,710.00	\$35,400.00	-
Greece	\$944.00	\$354.00	\$1,652.00	\$293,466.00	\$16,520.00	-
Hungary	\$6,372.00	\$1,062.00	\$5,664.00	\$240,484.00	\$24,662.00	-
Ireland	\$4,484.00	\$826.00	\$5,664.00	\$461,380.00	\$19,352.00	\$22.00
Italy	\$6,726.00	\$1,298.00	\$7,198.00	\$438,488.00	\$31,978.00	-
Latvia	\$1,652.00	\$236.00	\$2,360.00	\$136,526.00	\$10,148.00	-
Lithuania	\$2,124.00	\$236.00	\$2,832.00	\$168,858.00	\$13,452.00	-
Luxembourg	\$10,266.00	\$3,186.00	\$11,564.00	\$792,370.00	\$45,194.00	-
Malta	\$826.00	\$472.00	\$2,596.00	\$289,572.00	\$9,676.00	-
Netherlands	\$7,788.00	\$2,242.00	\$15,340.00	\$498,550.00	\$38,940.00	-
Norway	\$2,360.00	\$354.00	\$2,950.00	\$365,328.00	\$14,160.00	\$52.00
Poland	\$4,602.00	\$708.00	\$6,608.00	\$205,910.00	\$24,662.00	-
Portugal	\$1,534.00	\$590.00	\$4,130.00	\$306,210.00	\$18,172.00	\$7.00
Romania	\$2,596.00	\$472.00	\$2,360.00	\$34,456.00	\$3,540.00	-
Slovakia	\$6,136.00	\$826.00	\$5,782.00	\$229,156.00	\$24,780.00	-
Slovenia	\$7,906.00	\$1,652.00	\$7,316.00	\$310,222.00	\$25,724.00	\$19.00
Spain	\$3,068.00	\$472.00	\$5,074.00	\$353,528.00	\$19,470.00	-
Sweden	\$2,596.00	\$354.00	\$3,304.00	\$416,068.00	\$16,166.00	\$131.00
Switzerland	\$10,856.00	\$2,124.00	\$10,384.00	\$524,864.00	\$34,692.00	\$86.00
United Kingdom	\$4,602.00	\$1,298.00	\$7,788.00	\$459,138.00	\$28,674.00	\$24.00

Fig. 15. Results with maximum EI cost scenario.

Fig. 16. Results with minimum EI cost scenario.

Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 show the results of the sensitivity of the environmental impact on the decision-making. The results still show that hybrid system is more beneficial than two other options, in particular, the benefit is more remarkable when the environmental impact costs are the highest.

3.4. Comparison with conventional MCDA process

In order to investigate the adequacy of the proposed method, this section was to compare the results of the proposed method to the conventional MCDA process using AHP method. Fig. 17 shows the general process of the AHP method applicable to this case study. In this process, the

impact of risk assessment remains as a form of RPNs, whilst those of economic assessment and environmental assessment are expressed monetary values. To make different units to be compared, it is followed by the process of the normalization where the impact values are converted into percentage (%) by comparison with other models. To reflect the decision-makers preferences, the process of scoring, and thereby different weighing factors on each criterion is made.

Fig. 17. Conventional MCDA using AHP method [36][45].

Fig. 18. Comparison of the results obtained from both the proposed method and conventional AHP method.

Fig. 18 shows the results obtained from the conventional AHP method. Now, that can be compared with the original results in Fig. 13. The fundamental difference between the proposed method and the AHP method is the unit of comparison: it is “cost (monetary value)” for the proposed method while it is “percentage” for the conventional method. In addition, conventional method is subject to the weighing factors on each category. Fig. 18 a) shows the results when the equal weighing factor was applied to each category, whilst Fig. 18 b) presents the results when cost impact is 3 times more favourable than other categories. Likewise, Fig. 18 c) shows the analytic results when environmental impact is 3 times more important than two

other categories. Lastly, Fig. 18 d) reveals the results when risk impact is 3 times more important than the other categories.

From this analysis, problems due to interdependencies between standards and alternatives can be found. There may be discrepancies between judgment and ranking criteria

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In general, it has been well-known that the DM propulsion system is more efficient than the DE propulsion system because the DE system inevitably has electrical loss to some extent during the process of transmitting electricity from the generators to the consumer. However, as investigating the performance of the short route ferry, the research findings show the optimal operation of batteries will increase the efficiency. The case study has proven that the excellence of the hybrid system in consideration of all the aspects – cost, environment, and risk. Results showed that the application of hybrid system, using batteries to support the conventional power system to a ship provides several advantages those can be summarized as below.

- 1) Relatively higher initial costs of hybrid systems could be covered by reducing energy consumption and engine maintenance during ship operation.
- 2) Hybrid systems can contribute to cleaner shipping as it reduces the air emissions.
- 3) Hybrid systems could enhance the safety and reliability of power system (more safe operation during the peak load)

On the other hand, this paper developed an optimal decision-making process for applying hybrid systems into marine vessels. Research findings revealed that this proposed framework is effective for MCDA from the economic, environmental and risk perspectives. It was shown that the benefit of this process was placed not only for selecting an optimal model among various ones but for evaluating the optimal uses by investigating the sensitivity of various

scenarios. In addition, it was found that the process of scenario selection also would enable us to investigate the sensitivity of parameters as the influence of prices of emissions was investigated on the final results.

Also, this paper has proven the subjectivity of the conventional MCDA process where the preference of stakeholder may mislead the conclusion, addressing the necessity of the verification work for weighting factors on the criteria.

Given this, it is believed that the proposed process has contributed to updating the reliability of the MCDA by removing the normalization process as providing a simpler and more straightforward decision-making process.

The application of the proposed MCDA framework is not necessarily limited to the hybrid ships or marine systems. The use of it can be surely extensive to the any other products and technologies in various industries wherever multi-criteria decision making is treated importantly. Nevertheless, it may be necessary to demonstrate the effectiveness of this process to other industries as a future research.

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